

IELTS Writing Revision Platform with Automated Essay Scoring and Adaptive Feedback

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Abstract—This paper presents the design, development, and evaluation of a proposed revision platform assisting candidates for the International English Language Testing System (IELTS) writing exam. Traditional IELTS preparation methods lack personalised feedback, catered to the IELTS writing rubric. To address these shortcomings, the platform features an attractive user interface (UI), an Automated Essay Scoring system (AES), and targeted feedback tailored to candidates and the IELTS writing rubric. The platform architecture separates conversational guidance from a dedicated writing interface to reduce cognitive load and simulate exam conditions. Through iterative, Design-Based Research (DBR) cycles, the study progressed from rule-based to transformer-based with a regression head scoring, mounted with adaptive feedback.

Early cycles (2-3) revealed fundamental limitations of rule-based approaches: mid-band compression, low accuracy, and negative R^2 values. DBR Cycle 4 implemented a DistilBERT transformer model with a regression head, yielding substantial improvements with MAE of 0.66 and positive R^2 . This enabled Cycle 5's adaptive feedback implementation, which demonstrated statistically significant score improvements (mean +0.060 bands, $p = 0.011$, Cohen's $d = 0.504$), though effectiveness varied by revision strategy. Findings suggest automated feedback functions are most suited as a supplement to human instruction, with conservative surface-level corrections proving more reliable than aggressive structural interventions for IELTS preparation contexts. Challenges remain in assessing higher-band essays, and future work should incorporate longitudinal studies with real IELTS candidates and validation from official examiners.

I. Introduction

The IELTS is known as the benchmark for English competence for academic and professional purposes, with over 3.5 million tests administered annually [1].

The IELTS exams are prerequisites for academic and professional opportunities in English-speaking countries, recognised by 11,000 organisations across 140 countries. They impact immigration, study, and work chances globally. Millions of students depend on their IELTS scores for life-changing opportunities, especially for higher education, where a minimum score of 6.5 is often required for admission [2].

The IELTS writing exam evaluates task achievement, coherence and cohesion, lexical analysis, and grammatical accuracy [3]. Task 1 requires analysis of visual data, while Task 2 involves constructing a piece of structured writing. Despite its importance, the writing portion consistently receives the lowest mean score across all candidate backgrounds. Shortcomings amongst candidates include question misinterpretation, insufficient elaboration, and weak argumentation. Historically consistent underperformance spotlights the need for targeted preparation tooling.

II. Literature Review

A. The Need for Adaptive IELTS Writing Preparation

The writing component of the IELTS assesses four criteria: Task Achievement (TA), Coherence and Cohesion (CC), Lexical Resource (LR), and Grammatical Range and Accuracy (GRA); yet it consistently yields the lowest average scores across test-taker cohorts [3]. Common challenges include question misinterpretation, limited vocabulary, recurring grammatical errors, and unfamiliarity with academic writing conventions. Traditional classroom preparation provides generalised instructions and delayed, instructor-dependent feedback that lacks personalisation, leaving learners unable to remediate individual weaknesses in real-time [3].

AI writing tools such as Grammarly have gained popularity for providing instant feedback on grammar, vocabulary, and structure, supplementing traditional teaching. Empirical studies show that using AI writing

tools leads to measurable performance improvements. Table I tabulates IELTS candidates' scores across all categories, which improved by integrating these writing tools into their workflow. This had a strong impact on the GRA criteria, with an average score increase of 1.2 points, resulting in an overall band score improvement of about one full band [4].

Table I: Pre-and Post-Writing Assessment Scores (Mean \pm SD) [4]

Band Descriptor	Pre-Test Mean \pm SD	Post-Test Mean \pm SD	Mean Difference	t-Value	p-Value
Task Achievement (TA)	5.5 \pm 0.6	6.5 \pm 0.5	1.0	9.81	< 0.001
Coherence & Cohesion (CC)	5.7 \pm 0.7	6.6 \pm 0.6	0.9	8.45	< 0.001
Lexical Resource (LR)	5.3 \pm 0.5	6.4 \pm 0.4	1.1	10.12	< 0.001
Grammatical Range & Accuracy (GRA)	5.4 \pm 0.6	6.6 \pm 0.5	1.2	11.37	< 0.001

Studies verify AI tools' capabilities to increase IELTS writing scores by about one band, with TA improving from 5.5 \pm 0.66 to 6.5 \pm 0.51 and GRA showing the highest gain (mean Δ = 1.2). However, overreliance on AI may hinder learning towards fundamental writing skills. Table 2 voices a survey of 60 IELTS candidates found that while they rated grammar correction (mean = 4.6) and ease of use (mean = 4.7) highly, they still preferred combining AI feedback with instructor guidance (mean = 4.5) [4].

Table II: Students' Perceptions of AI Tools (n=60) [4]

Statement	Mean \pm SD
The AI tool provided valuable feedback on grammar.	4.6 \pm 0.5
Using the AI tool helped me improve coherence in writing.	4.3 \pm 0.6
The AI tool improved my vocabulary usage.	4.4 \pm 0.5
The tool was easy to use and accessible.	4.7 \pm 0.4
I prefer using AI tools along with instructor feedback.	4.5 \pm 0.6

Recent advancements in adaptive educational technologies aim to address gaps by delivering personalised, calculated feedback aligned with the IELTS rubrics. Adaptive teaching systems analyse learners' strengths and weaknesses and adjust feedback accordingly, offering 24/7 support tailored to individual cognitive profiles [5]. For instance, Schipper validated that embedding adaptive feedback loops into linguistic lessons substantially augmented engagement and learning outcomes compared to static instruction [6]. Yet, few platforms incorporate adaptive feedback algorithms within systems supporting realistic writing interfaces. This gap motivates the development of a platform that provides adaptive feedback coordinated for IELTS writing practice.

B. Linguistic Tools and AI Support in Writing

Linguistic learning platforms have emerged to support ESL (English as a Second Language) learners in areas such as pronunciation, vocabulary, and grammar, aspects often overlooked in traditional ESL environments. Research conducted by Ibrahim concluded that ESL learners were hesitant to use tools like dictionaries, which they perceived as complex, highlighting the need for innovative solutions [7].

Notably, ELSA Speak and Duolingo are prominent tools that include immediate feedback and gamification elements to boost learner engagement. However, despite their advantages, both platforms are limited in handling complex writing tasks such as IELTS Task 2.

ELSA Speak is a successful language learning platform because users can concentrate on meaningful, relevant materials tailored to their profiles. It offers targeted, personalised exercises that focus on both segmental aspects (individual sounds) and suprasegmental features (intonation and stress) [8]. The platform performs real-time speech analytics to enhance fluency and intonation through interactive chatbot conversations. Its success stems from personalisation, a low-stress learning environment, and adherence to repetition and adaptive scaffolding, which are fundamental to language learning. Furthermore, ELSA Speak's chatbot avoids overwhelming learners by providing understandable outputs and fostering a healthy, minimal-stress learning environment without cognitive overload [9]. However, ELSA mainly concentrates on speaking skills and neglects other areas, such as writing, where IELTS candidates often underperform.

Another prominent linguistic platform is Duolingo, a globally recognised tool fusing gamification and mobile-assisted learning, supplying a rich collection of accessible language courses [10]. Research performed by Laksanasut observed Duolingo's embodiment of gamification aspects deep-rooted in Self-Determination Theory (SDT), which contributed to high motivation, minimised anxiety, and high user retention through daily goals, a reward system, and progress tracking [11]. Duolingo's SDT gamification approach increases user persistence; however, its lack of depth disqualifies Duolingo as an adequate tool for achieving the academic writing and argumentative complexity required by the IELTS writing tasks.

Both tools lack the depth of contextualised feedback and targeted IELTS writing support necessary to prepare candidates. However, ELSA's personalised AI feedback and exercise generation, paired with Duolingo's gamification mechanics, model the skeleton of a holistic, writing-oriented platform.

C. Conversational Agents in Education

Within educational environments, conversational agents and chatbot systems have emerged as a favoured preparation technique, especially for examinations such as the IELTS. Generalised preparation is common in traditional classrooms, neglecting diverse learning paces, especially for IELTS candidates who may not identify their linguistic weaknesses due to inflexibility. Adaptive chatbots, utilising natural language processing (NLP), provide continuous access to targeted feedback, thereby addressing challenges of generalisation [12]. Chatbot technologies, originating with ELIZA in 1964, have evolved to simulate interactive, meaningful communication, enhancing learner engagement through dialogue practice and instant feedback.

Research spearheaded by Lin into the architecture of chatbot systems, as exemplified by the JULIE chatbot in construction management, illustrates the sophistication possible through entity matching and integration with structured databases [13]. By processing both structured and unstructured data from formats such as spreadsheets, documents, and webpages, it enables the answering of broad user queries while still providing precise, contextual answers [13].

Chatbot architectures like JULIE can be integrated into linguistic contexts such as IELTS to boost candidates' confidence by supporting structured question-answering and personalised responses to the exam.

D. NLP Tools In IELTS Preparation

A study by Muhammad demonstrated Google Dialogflow's excellent consistency in constructing chatbots in a controlled environment with high accuracy, as evidenced by perfect performance in structured domains, such as hotel check-ins, as shown in Fig. 1, scoring 100% across all typical procedures, such as passport handling, checking in, thank you, and hello messages [14].

Studies by Sung and Kang illustrated Dialogflow's potential as a chatbot system in an English as a Foreign Language (EFL) setting. Dialogflow balances linguistic complexity with predictable responses, enabling controlled language generation that minimised hallucinations and maintains contextual relevance, which addresses fundamental challenges in language education that traditional classrooms cannot replicate [15].

However, while Abdelmoiz found DialogFlow’s metrics impressive in controlled environments [16], the system’s reliance on structured, predictable patterns makes it poorly suited to the IELTS exam, which requires adaptive, context-aware feedback.

An experiment at Thammasat University assessed writing prep methods: ChatGPT supplemented vs. traditional, led by Bai. Fig. 2 displays that Pre-test scores were 5.17 (experimental) and 5.22 (control). After prep, experimental scores rose to 5.8025, control to 5.3. The score difference is credited to ChatGPT's influence, also hinting at how ineffective traditional methods were in comparison [17].

Table III: Pre-and Post-Writing Assessment Scores (Mean \pm SD) [17]

	GROUP	AVERAGE	STANDARD DEVIATION
PRE-Test	Experimental Group	5.17	0.4781
	Control Group	5.22	0.4202
POST-Test	Experimental Group	5.8025	0.51
	Control Group	5.3	0.7302

Bai’s study qualitatively dissected the factors contributing to the superior quality of writing crafted by the experimental group. Core reasons identified by Bai included the momentous expansion of students’ vocabulary, with the introduction of terms like ‘celebration’, ‘symbolise’, ‘atmosphere’, and ‘advertisement’. Additionally, perfections in writing format and structure directly reflected the increase in writing scores [17].

While Bai's study demonstrated solid results regarding ChatGPT's integration into linguistic writing preparation, Moran voiced underlying concerns of students utilising such tools, arguing that over-reliance on Generative AI risks inhibiting the development of an authentic writing voice, leaving students “insecure and alienated about their verbal abilities” [18].

The popularity of ChatGPT in education is growing, but relying solely on it for IELTS prep hinders candidates' abilities since models can't replicate the human communication skills required in IELTS testing.

E. Designing Interfaces for Feedback and Learning

The user interface and system layout impact how learners interpret and utilise the feedback delivered. We compare the platform designs of a website versus a web application to determine which one better supports chatbots, automated scoring, and adaptive feedback. The stereotypical website is well-suited to static and semi-interactive resources, for instance, ASR-assisted materials, but these lack the stateful, interactive flows necessary in orchestrating conversation, ongoing scoring, and adaptive feedback [19].

To accomplish this functionality, implementing persistent state and event-driven pipelines is necessary, which surpasses the capabilities of a static website ecosystem. The web application architecture is more supportive of stateful interactions without requiring any installs and scales, empowering users to execute tasks and retrieve feedback [20].

The platform enables easy incorporation of features such as chatbots, submission grading, and adaptive feedback loops tailored to the IELTS. Ultimately, a web application was chosen, with a UI designed to aid ESL learners in regulating cognitive load, maximising engagement, and focusing on learning outcomes.

Futile UIs encourage strenuous cognitive load, which in turn degrades timed-task performance, through inadequate, unclear navigation and task framing, which are imperative to IELTS candidates aiming for high writing standards.

Due to human biological nature, working memory is limited, carefully crafted UIs strictly avoid splitting attention and eliminating ambiguity to optimise cognitive abilities for task performance [21].

Specifically targeting cognitive design principles, we prioritised visual hierarchy (typography, spacing, grouping) to streamline attention and task flow. Crafting devoted wireframes validated that the UI is functional, engaging, and reduces task complications, and maximises candidates' problem-solving abilities [22].

While chatbots can foster engagement with social interaction, they are less applicable to the IELTS writing exercise, which requires transparency, structure, and concentration.

Complete reliance on a chatbot interface risks increasing cognitive load and losing engagement. This informed the decision to transcend a pure chatbot interface, dedicating a UI solely to the writing exercise while being mindful of visual hierarchy, engagement, and cognitive load to aid candidates' examination success.

III. Proposed Framework

A. Introduction to the Proposed Framework

Figure 1: IELTS Preparation Platform Framework.

Fig. 1 illustrates the proposed IELTS Preparation platform framework, including dialogue systems, adaptive feedback mechanisms, and a dedicated IELTS writing exercise screen, within a web application architecture. The framework domains consists of: (1) chatbot conversational dialogue system, (2) adaptive feedback mechanisms based on the IELTS rubric, and (3) writing exercise interface. The subsequent sections describe the domains, their intersections, and their impact on candidates.

1. *Conversational Dialogue:* The conversation dialogue domain is built using Microsoft Bot Framework, adopting a scaffold comprising of a welcoming interaction, prompting users to provide details such as name and age to establish familiarity. Users are then presented with a preview card of an IELTS writing task, and the ability to select which portion they would like to begin with first (introduction, body, or conclusion). They are then guided into the main Writing Task UI, focusing on their chosen part. Each submission is graded, providing adaptive feedback, an estimated grade, and actionable suggestions. By decomposing the IELTS writing task into smaller, manageable parts, the chatbot reduces cognitive load, alleviates anxiety, and fosters a supportive learning environment.
2. *Adaptive Feedback:* The adaptive feedback mechanism focuses on providing precise evaluations of candidate submissions by comparing them against the IELTS rubric, clearly pinpointing strengths and weaknesses. Behind the scenes, the mechanism operates using NLP tools including BERT, SpaCy,

and NLTK, which identify grammatical errors, measure vocabulary difficulty, and evaluate coherence. Founding a continuous, guided learning environment that adjusts to the candidate’s current skill level, which reduces cognitive load and helps candidates progressively develop their English writing abilities.

3. *IELTS Writing Exercise UI*: The IELTS Writing Exercise UI was created to help candidates focus on their writing, reducing distractions and cognitive load. ESL candidates benefit from a distraction-free practice environment. To support this, the platform provides clear instructions, a reference image, and a large writing space to maximise focus on the task. All features, including submissions, progress tracking, grading, and adaptive feedback, are accessible through a dismissible sidebar. Adhering to cognitive load and visual hierarchy principles, guiding the user’s attention to key objectives. This core interface connects user interactions, adaptive feedback, and automated grading, while promoting self-study strategies essential for IELTS success.
4. *Platform Architecture*: The IELTS preparation platform features a web application architecture that uses a React frontend alongside backend services dedicated to processing, scoring, and providing adaptive feedback. This setup enhances gamification elements such as progress tracking, achievement systems, and adaptive feedback, supporting sustained high motivation levels during learning. The React components handle all user interactions, including the welcoming chatbot dialogue, writing submissions, adaptive feedback cards, and scoring. Meanwhile, the backend services offer endpoints that integrate NLP models responsible for scoring and adaptive feedback algorithms. The separation of frontend and backend, along with the web application's design, maximises system scalability, fault tolerance, and future maintainability, creating a comprehensive IELTS preparation experience for candidates.

B. Conversational Dialogue Component Analysis

The conversational dialogue guides candidates into the writing interface, deliberately creating a highly task-focused environment by breaking down the writing task with a preview card that displays the initial sections of the IELTS writing task (introduction, body, and conclusion). This increases user engagement and familiarity with the platform. Conversational dialogues have already proven successful within linguistic platforms such as ELSA Speak, establishing low-friction, learner-friendly environments that foster high engagement and motivation [9].

Figure 2: Conversational Dialogue Architecture.

Fig. 2 illustrates the main dialogue architecture of the chatbot designed to guide users into the writing exercise ecosystem, created using the MBF Azure chatbot. The dialogue begins when a user loads the system, followed by a greeting and prompts for their name and age, simulating a typical human conversation. Framing interactions in a familiar manner, initiating interaction with the linguistic platform.

After completing the welcome dialogue, the exercise flow begins. The chatbot asks if the user wants to start an IELTS exercise. If the user agrees, a preview card shows the exercise options, allowing them to select a writing section. The selected section then guides the user into the main practice environment. This flow keeps users engaged by breaking the interaction into focused, manageable parts, helping them stay alert and involved throughout the session.

MBF's architecture provides leeway within user responses, aiding in constructing an education chatbot specifically for IELTS preparation, delivering interactive 24/7 learning support, aspects crucial for a valuable chatbot [12].

C. Adaptive Feedback Mechanism Analysis

The adaptive feedback mechanism distributes feedback catered to candidate writing strengths and weaknesses compared to the IELTS writing assessment rubric: TA, CC, LR, and GRA. Through rubric decomposition, the feedback mechanism is better able to pinpoint candidate strengths and weaknesses. Enabling a cyclical improvement loop, steering away from non-directional self-assessment.

Adaptive feedback provides two main advantages. First, it helps maintain high motivation and engagement by offering iterative improvements based on user performance. Secondly, it enhances traditional feedback by delivering customised guidance that can help improve writing scores. Embedded within the writing exercises, adaptive feedback promotes ongoing improvement and keeps users focused throughout practice sessions.

Figure 3: Adaptive Feedback Mechanism Architecture.

Fig. 3 illustrates how user submissions are processed via the adaptive feedback system, which provides predicted band scores, areas for improvement, and sample corrections. This mechanism is built on official IELTS samples and human-rated Kaggle datasets, which train a NLP model to deliver precise predictions and analysis in alignment with the scoring rubric.

Research by Reyes is supportive of including an adaptive feedback system, demonstrating that algorithm-driven adaptive teaching enhances motivation, engagement, and performance [5]. In the classroom, adaptive feedback addresses the lack of personalised learning paths common in traditional methods, offering consistent, accessible, and formative support instead [6]. Linguistic platforms with adaptive feedback have historically experienced higher retention rates.

Adaptive feedback is imperial for effective IELTS preparation. It identifies gaps and readjustments based on

user performance, guiding candidates to improve their scores according to the IELTS rubric. This approach helps candidates understand key writing qualities such as structure, vocabulary, and grammar in an exam context [23] [24].

Currently, no existing linguistic platform exactly replicates the IELTS examiner rubric, which highlights the importance of an IELTS writing practice platform.

D. Writing Interface Component Analysis

The IELTS writing interface offers candidates an undisturbed self-study platform reducing cognitive load.

IELTS Writing - Task 1 - Question 3/6

Enter Focus Mode

Task Instructions

The graph above shows population growth in different regions. Write a report describing the key features and make comparisons where relevant. You should write at least 150 words.

- Time Allowed: 20 minutes
- Minimum Words: 150

Introduction Guidelines:

- Paraphrase the main question
- Provide an overview of the graph
- Use appropriate academic language

Tip: A strong introduction should paraphrase the question and provide a general overview without specific data.

Where they live	Number of people living in each other's country					Total
	British	German	Italian	Polish	Spanish	
Britain	297,000	119,000	556,000	71,000	1,037,000	
Germany	104,000		556,000	426,000	112,000	1,198,000
Italy	79,000	42,000		106,000	19,000	196,000
Poland	760	4,400	670		170	6,000
Spain	391,000	196,000	188,000	86,000		861,000
Total	524,760	539,000	863,670	1,168,000	202,170	3,298,000

therefore, thus, consequently)

Vocabulary & Word Choice [View Details](#)

Vocabulary & Word Choice Score **6.6/9.0**

Unique Words **37** Lexical Diversity **0.90%**

Feedback: No specific feedback available

Grammar & Sentence Structure [Show Analysis](#) [View Details](#)

Grammar Score **8.8/9.0**

Feedback: Excellent grammar with sophisticated structures.

Task Achievement [View Details](#)

Task Achievement Score **4.1/9.0**

Task Requirements Met

Effective use of Position markers, for example: "While

Select section to write: Introduction

Auto-saved 2:13:50 PM

Technology has significantly transformed modern society, influencing communication, education, and work. While some argue that it enhances productivity and connectivity, others believe it leads to distractions and a decline in critical thinking skills. Discuss both perspectives and provide your own argument.

41 words 309 chars

Total word count: 41/150 (minimum)

Figure 4: IELTS Revision Platform Writing Interface.

As shown in Fig. 4, the interface features task instructions accompanied by a reference image, a spacious writing area, and a dismissible sidebar. The sidebar manages submissions, tracks progress, and provides adaptive feedback, creating a loop for skill improvement. By breaking down tasks and providing a structured layout, the interface decreases anxiety.

The success of the writing interface relies on cognitive load theory and visual hierarchy principles, which improve usability. Fang and Bueno-Vesga's research shows that unorganised interfaces increase mental strain, particularly targeting working memory limits, leading to lower engagement and retention rates, especially for second-language learners [21] [25].

Mohamed's study supports that a clear layout with deliberate spacing and navigation enhances user attention and understanding, and wireframing beforehand ensures system functionality with minimal friction [22]. Limpanopparat's research indicates engagement peaks with intuitive navigation when employing tactics such as objective-aligned content and responsive feedback mechanisms [26].

These factors led to choosing a dedicated writing interface over a chatbot for IELTS prep, as it offers higher immersion, motivation, and persistence.

IV. System Implementation

Our motivation for creating an IELTS preparation platform arises from the need to offer English learners realistic and progressive practice opportunities. Traditionally, IELTS preparation has focused on conventional classroom settings or self-study using online resources. However, this approach has resulted in a lack of targeted, actionable feedback and time-limited support, which can lead to poor exam performance.

Ongoing issues such as difficulty receiving criteria-related feedback, ineffective self-study, and heightened anxiety during exams prompted the development of this platform. The platform was designed with four clear objectives outlined in Table IV.

Table IV: Proposed System Goals and Core Functionalities

Goals	Core Functionalities
IELTS Exam Simulation	Realistic conditions (timed task, task format, dedicated input field)
IELTS Writing Rubric Aligned Adaptive Feedback	Automated, accurate scoring paired with actionable feedback into Task Achievement, Coherence and Cohesion, Lexical Resource, and Grammar
Minimal Cognitive Load through UI/UX best practices	UI/UX incorporating visual hierarchy principles, channelling candidate focus to the writing task
Guarantee Easy Expansion through an isolated, modular system architecture	Separation of concerns (React frontend, Chatbot middleware, Python backend), enabling distributed deployment

1. *System Performance:* To maintain high and stable student engagement, it is essential to optimise performance. An unresponsive system can compromise learners' focus, motivation, and may discourage further study. This is especially true for our adaptive feedback mechanism, which processes candidate submissions using intensive computations. Therefore, to ensure a highly efficient system, performance optimisation techniques such as asynchronous operations and threading must be employed. Research by Qun on retention rates in Chinese EFL learners further supports this prioritisation of system performance, linking immediate feedback to high student engagement and performance [27]. Conversely, delayed feedback encourages deeper, longer reflection, which is less suited to our system.
2. *Extensibility:* The system must be adept for expansion; therefore, adherence to best practices is vital across the platform's codebase. Within our platform, best practices are present via separation of concerns, where the React frontend, the adaptive feedback mechanism, and the chatbot are all loosely coupled components. The platform benefits from the best practices being followed, enabling the addition and or removal of features independent of the entire system [28]. Granting our platform the ability to evolve and adapt over time in response to the feedback provided by candidates.
3. *Scalability:* Alongside Extensibility, our system must maintain performance as user numbers grow, while ensuring core functionalities like UI rendering, adaptive feedback, and automated scoring remain fast. Addressing scalability challenges is essential to maximise the value delivered to candidates [29].

Figure 5: Revision Platform Workflow.

Fig. 5 shows the system workflow diagram, which presents core objectives from Table IV in a logical, user-friendly way, prioritising the user's experience. The user is welcomed, followed by an interactive writing task interface simulating an examination, featuring tasks, hints, and a dedicated writing area, meeting a core objectives outlined in Table IV.

After the user successfully submits their attempt, it is assessed against the IELTS rubric criteria, generating a predicted band score (1-9) and a grading percentage (0-100%), along with feedback specific to the submission, including strong points, weak points, and suggestions.

Our linguistic platform is designed for distributed deployment, with a focus on maintaining high responsiveness and scalability. We use Docker to isolate and contain NLP components, making them accessible and interactive throughout the UI utilising asynchronous messaging queues. This approach ensures low latency for users and quick access to adaptive feedback, automated grading, and submission times. By doing so, we can reduce excessive NLP workflows, maintain low latency, and accommodate scaling as our user base grows.

The UI presents NLP results via modal and sidebar components, including overall grade, attempts left, exit option, and adaptive feedback preview, all organised to reduce cognitive load and focus the user on the writing task. It enforces a three-attempt limit to improve submission quality and reduce NLP processing load, automatically progressing the user or ending with final grading and feedback.

Table V: System Implementation Specification

Component	Technology	Version	Purpose
User Interface	React	v18.2+	Rendering UI components and managing user interactions.
Conversational AI	Microsoft Bot Framework	SDK v4.22.0 & .NET 6	Chatbot dialogue for onboarding and navigating towards the writing exercise.
System Backend	FastAPI & Python	v3.10	REST API endpoints, Adaptive Feedback Retrieval, and database integration.
NLP Processing	BERT (Transformers)	v4.x	Text comparison against the IELTS mark scheme and adaptive feedback generation.
Relational Database	PostgreSQL	v14+	Store user progress, submissions, results, and feedback.
Analytical Database	Firebase	v13.1+	Collect analytics and interaction logs for feature evaluation.
Cloud Hosting	Azure/AWS	Latest	Scalable hosting with load balancing and autoscaling.

Table V details the technologies and versions for system reproducibility and to encourage future project development. Strategies currently cemented into the platform include distributed and heterogeneous workloads that are managed to ensure the capability of handling demanding workloads, such as asynchronous operations to optimise NLP pipelines, and common practices within high-performance computing (HPC) environments [30]. Additionally, decoupling components through leveraging a modular architecture throughout the codebase improves maintainability, extensibility, and scalability [31].

Our system will undergo assessments of technical and educational metrics. Technical evaluations entail stress testing and performance measurements, spotlighting areas such as latency, scalability, and system reliability to determine whether the system can simulate IELTS practice under realistic workloads. Educational evaluations assess the credibility of the IELTS learning and preparation benefits provided to candidates. This will be done by benchmarking the automated grading, actionable insights, and adaptive feedback. Additionally, the interface will be aligned with UX/UI principles for pedagogical purposes, primarily reducing cognitive load for users.

Although user studies are currently outside the scope, our evaluation strategies will still highlight the platform's reliability and educational validity. The methodology and experimental procedures will be discussed in more detail in Section V (Methodology).

V. METHODOLOGY

This study conducts a design-based research (DBR) approach to develop, test, and refine a linguistic platform specific to IELTS writing preparation. As communicated by Collins, DBR unifies design and research, enabling crafting technical artefacts while investigating their educational impact [32].

Technical evaluation adhered to performance and load testing principles for web applications [33], including unit, end-to-end, latency, and benchmark testing of the automated grading, user interface, and adaptive feedback features using mimicking candidate submissions.

Through the combination of software engineering with pedagogical evaluation, DBR ensures the platform's technical reliability and educational validity. Aligning UI designs with best practices such as visual hierarchy

[22], cognitive load reduction [25], and applying principles of self-determination theory (SDT) [11] to maximise candidate problem-solving capabilities.

A. DBR Cycle 1

The initial DBR cycle aimed to establish the foundational modular architecture of the IELTS preparation platform. This involved developing early prototypes of the UI, MBF chatbot, and Python NLP-based automated grading and adaptive feedback key platform components.

The visual hierarchy of the UI was designed based on principles blending both cognitive load theory [21] and SDT [11] to optimise candidate focus, clarity, reduce mental load, and reward candidate effort. This approach ensured the platform was clear, accessible, and user-friendly, thereby encouraging greater motivation to study.

The first DBR cycle resulted in a working prototype capable of collecting user input, grading responses, and providing adaptive feedback. This laid a strong technical and pedagogical foundation for subsequent DBR cycles.

The second DBR cycle assessed the technical accuracy and pedagogical consistency of the IELTS preparation platform. Since the platform includes an automated feedback system, it was crucial to ensure that its outputs align with IELTS examiners' standards to provide candidates with trustworthy guidance [34].

B. DBR Cycle 2

The diagnosis strategy covered three testing areas. First, unit testing using Jest [35], Pytest [36], and xUnit [37] checked components like chatbot dialogues, user interface, and grading services.

Secondly, end-to-end testing simulated user workflows using Cypress [38] from chatbot greeting to submission, ensuring smoothness. Lastly, benchmarking assessed NLP model predictions against a Kaggle IELTS dataset [39], measuring accuracy and discrepancies.

This cycle exposed limitations in strict grammar grading, inconsistencies in LR, and underestimating higher-band essays.

These findings helped guide the subsequent cycle, focusing on remediating grading and feedback methods, aligning with IELTS exam standards, and enhancing pedagogical effectiveness.

C. DBR Cycle 3

The third DBR cycle focused on implementing fixes for weaker areas identified in the cycle 2. Remediation targeted three regions. First, the CoLA grammar model [40], which was less consistent in analysing and identifying errors, was replaced with Python's LanguageTool API [41], providing evaluations that adhere more closely to the IELTS Grammatical Accuracy and Range rubric.

This provided more IELTS-appropriate evaluations within the GRA criteria [41]. Second, the LR classification process was remodeled to incorporate word sophistication ratios [42] instead of relying solely on academic vocabulary frequency.

Lastly, the task achievement grading algorithm was reformulated to mitigate the issue of low scores assigned when submissions did not meet the 250-word count requirement, introducing a linear scaling model to grade submissions up to the word limit.

To gauge remediation effectiveness, the automated grading system was re-evaluated using benchmark testing on 100 pre-scored essays from the Kaggle IELTS dataset [39].

Performance metrics included mean absolute error (MAE), coefficient of determination (R^2), and the percentage of predictions within ± 0.5 IELTS bands of expert scores.

D. DBR Cycle 4

The fourth DBR cycle addressed the limitations of rule-based and hybrid scoring methods for grading IELTS writing essays.

While cycle 3 improved scoring for GRA, LR, and TA, grading was still not reflective of the full range. There were underpredictions of higher-band essays and a tendency to cluster grades around the middle bands. Investigation revealed that the rule-based AES system could be deceived by longer essays and complex vocabulary, exposing its poor generalisation, an issue common to many AES algorithms [43].

In response, Cycle 4 shifted to a lightweight transformer-based model with a regression head, specifically DistilBERT, to enhance predictive accuracy, guided by previous research led by Ludwig investigating transformers' suitability for AES [44].

The choice to adopt a Transformer architecture stemmed from the underperformance of previous rule-based approach and the researched advantages of pre-trained language models in AES. Traditional models relying on features like word counts and sentence length often struggle to capture complex writing styles, such as rhetorical structures or medium-level techniques [44].

Studies show that transformer models outperform regression-based methods, especially for tasks involving style, coherence, and context-areas difficult for simpler approaches [44]. This improvement directly influenced DBR Cycle 5, which focused on implementing adaptive feedback. Accurate predictions are crucial; inaccurate scores could lead to misleading feedback, hindering learners' progress and damaging the platform's credibility.

Each essay is tokenised using the standard DistilBERT tokeniser and is either truncated or padded to a fixed maximum length of 256 tokens. This process ensures consistent input size while preserving most of the essay's content.

The resulting tokens are fed into a pretrained encoder to generate contextualised embeddings; the pooled representation is then concatenated with a vector of manually extracted linguistic features (such as word count, sentence length, lexical diversity, and punctuation density), which are modelled through our iterations in DBR Cycles 2 and 3. Research indicates that hybrid models combining deep embeddings with explicit linguistic indicators often outperform models that rely solely on features or embeddings [45].

A linear regression head on top of this combined representation produces a continuous score predicting the IELTS band. Framing band prediction as a regression, rather than a classification, maintains the ordinal and constant nature of the scoring system and has been shown to improve calibration in automated scoring systems [46].

To balance expressive power and generalisation, the model is trained using the AdamW optimiser with a learning rate of 1.5×10^{-5} , weight decay of 0.02, and batch-size adjustments via gradient accumulation to simulate an effective larger batch while remaining memory efficient.

Dropout rate of 0.35, gentle label smoothing, and partial freezing of the encoder layers are applied to mitigate overfitting, a common challenge when fine-tuning large pretrained models on modestly sized essay datasets. Early stopping on validation MAE with patience monitoring ensures the selection of a model that generalises beyond training data. This balanced regularisation regime follows best practices identified in AES research using Transformer models, ensuring robust performance without excessive memorisation [47].

The dataset was randomly partitioned into 70% training, 15% validation, and 15% test, provisioning reliable hyperparameter tuning while preserving an independent final evaluation [39]. The training was run for up to 30 epochs, with early stopping based on validation MAE to prevent overfitting [48].

To evaluate cycle 4's scoring model, we followed AES research practices.

We assessed Mean Absolute Error (MAE) for average deviation, R^2 for variance explained, and accuracy within ± 0.5 and ± 1.0 IELTS bands [49].

We also used Pearson's correlation coefficient (PCC) and Spearman's (ρ) to measure linear and monotonic relationships [49]. ρ is especially important for ordinal IELTS bands, as it checks whether the model preserves the scoring order.

These metrics collectively provide a clear overview of accuracy, distribution, and order preservation, enabling transparent assessment of the Cycle 4 model.

E. DBR Cycle 5

The fifth DBR cycle centred on implementing and validating adaptive feedback based on the transformer-based grading model from Cycle 4.

While earlier cycles focused on achieving grading accuracy and aligning with rubrics, Cycle 5 explored if algorithmic feedback could facilitate meaningful score improvements through simulated candidate revisions [50].

To prevent data leakage and ensure fair assessment, a subset of 30 IELTS Writing Task 2 essays was selected from an external dataset not used in training, validation, or testing during Cycle 4. These essays were sourced from a publicly available IELTS evaluation corpus [51], ensuring they were unseen data.

The transformer model from Cycle 4 was retained as a fixed scoring component during Cycle 5, so score changes could be attributed solely to the feedback mechanism, not model retraining or drift. Adaptive feedback generation reused algorithms from Cycles 2 and 3, with prioritisation and targeting now guided by the predicted band score and associated linguistic feature deviations of the transformer model [46].

An evaluation process consisting of three steps was used to ensure fairness, reproducibility, and independence from prior training effects. First, each essay was scored with the transformer-based regression model, producing a continuous IELTS band prediction used as a baseline.

Second, adaptive feedback was retrieved based on strengths and weaknesses in IELTS Writing criteria: Grammatical Range and Accuracy, Lexical Resource, Coherence and Cohesion, and Task Achievement. This feedback was informed by the predicted score and linguistic deviations, targeting specific writing aspects likely to improve the band score.

Finally, feedback was applied through candidate persona revision behaviours, and the revised essays were rescored with the same model and preprocessing pipeline, mirroring the initial evaluation process. This closed-loop approach operationalises DBR principles by embedding theory-informed feedback and immediately assessing its instructional impact under controlled conditions.

Table VI: Candidate Revision Personas

Persona	Band Level	Revision Style	Compliance Level	Revision Actions
P1	6.5	Surface edits	High	Grammar, spelling, and punctuation fixes. Never restructure essays.
P2	6.5–6.8	Structural	Medium	Frequent paragraph splitting. Implement topic sentences. Minimalistic vocab editing.
P3	6.8	Selective	Low–Medium	Implements only 1–2 feedback suggestions, ignores the rest of the feedback.
P4	7.0	Coherence Focus	High	Improves sentence flow. Applies paragraph logical connectors. Avoidant of fancy vocab.
P5	6.7	Conservative	Medium	Safe edits, avoid sentence rewrites or new ideas.

To ensure candidate behaviour was controllable and reproducible, Cycle 5 simulated typical IELTS revision strategies using five personas [52], each with an initial band range, revision style, and compliance level with the feedback (see Table VI). Six essays from the locked 30 essay dataset were randomly assigned to each persona, and each person applied adaptive feedback according to their assigned compliance and style, clearly outlining permissible edits. This setup allowed for a systematic evaluation of how different revision tactics influenced feedback effectiveness without uncontrolled or inconsistent edits.

VI. RESULTS

A. Benchmarking Metrics Across DBR Cycles

Table VII summarises benchmarking results for DBR Cycle 2 and Cycle 3, measuring post-remediation using statistical metrics to evaluate grading performance, variance, and deviation against the pre-scored dataset.

Table VII: Metrics across DBR Cycles 2 & 3

Metric	DBR Cycle 2	DBR Cycle 3	Δ Improvement
Exact Match (%)	13%	17%	4%
Within ± 0.5 band (%)	47%	60%	13%
R^2	-0.0242	-0.0052	0.019
Mean Average Error (MAE)	1.27 bands	1.14 bands	0.013 bands

As Table VII shows, DBR Cycle 2 demonstrated poor grading reliability: only 13% of predictions matched the exact band, with 47% falling within ± 0.5 bands. The MAE of 14.10% and negative R^2 (-0.0242) indicated the model performed worse than simply predicting the mean score, necessitating significant refinement.

Cycle 3 remediations focused on algorithmic refinement of GRA, LR, and TA evaluation. Exact band matches rose to 17% (+4%), and ± 0.5 bands accuracy rose to 60% (+13%). MAE improved to 12.64%, and R^2 moved closer to zero (-0.0052), though remained negative.

Despite improvements, the model retained a mid-band bias (6.0–6.5), suggesting limited generalisation stemming from its lexical diversity weighting. Importantly, the persistently negative R^2 in both cycles showed the model performed worse than simply predicting the mean score. Though MAE dropped 1.46%, it remained above acceptable thresholds for accurate assessment, exposing limitations in the rule-based architecture.

We then visualised the predictions versus actual scores (scatter plots, confusion matrices, and box plots) to encapsulate remediation effects.

B. Visual Benchmark Analysis of DBR Cycle 2

Figure 6: (Cycle 2) Scatter plot of actual vs predicted IELTS band scores.

Most predictions cluster around the 5.5-6.5 range, evidencing that the model is reliable for mid-range essays. However, the model tends to underpredict essays around the 7.5-9.0 range, as points fall below the diagonal.

Figure 7: (Cycle 2). Confusion matrix of actual vs predicted bands.

Most predictions ranged from 5.5 to 6.5 bands, indicating that the model does not fully capture the entire score distribution as needed.

Figure 8: (Cycle 2). Box plots of actual vs predicted scores.

The actual scores span from 5.0 to 9.0, whereas the predicted scores are grouped tightly around 6.0-6.5, underscoring the model’s inability to capture the true dataset variation.

Holistically, Figs 6-8 establish that the Cycle 2 model iteration is only partially reliable, grading mid-band essays convincingly, but inconsistently grading higher-band submissions. These findings motivated the Cycle 3 remediations.

C. Post-Remediation Benchmarking and Visual Analysis (DBR Cycle 3)

Built on the Cycle 2 analysis, we applied targeted remediations to GRA, LR, and TA scoring. We substituted the CoLA grammar model with Python’s LanguageTool API to obtain a grading better correlated with the IELTS rubric, followed by enriching LR to account for word sophistication. Finally, we altered the TA grading to incorporate a linear scaling model, reducing bias against shorter essays. We then re-benchmarked the model on the same 100 pre-scored essays to fairly evaluate the impact of the remediations performed under identical conditions.

Table VII confirms advancements were made across all categories. The exact score matching increased from 13% to 17%, and within ± 0.5 , the precision increased from 47% to 60%. MAE decreased by 1.46%, and R^2 became much less negative.

The superior metrics revealed that the remediations augmented the model’s grading accuracy and reliability.

Figure 9: (Cycle 3). Scatter plot of actual vs predicted scores post-remediation.

Predictions illustrated scoring closer with actual scores, especially in the 5.5-7.0 range, validating the recalibrations applied to the GRA, LR, and TA scoring algorithms. Nevertheless, the model’s underprediction for 7.5-9.0 essays persisted, so further improvements were required.

Figure 10: (Cycle 3). Box plots of actual vs predicted scores post-remediation.

The predicted range has better coverage of the actual scores after remediation, yet predictions still group in the 5.5-7.0 range. This clustering signifies that the model is unable to handle high-quality (8.0-9.0) essays.

D. Benchmarking Metrics for DBR Cycle 4 (DistilBERT Regression Model)

Looking back at the results from Cycles 2 and 3, it was apparent that the rule-based algorithms had a performance ceiling within an AES context, constraining the accuracy and effectiveness of the adaptive feedback once activated, even after remediation.

Cycle 4 focused on developing the necessary driver for adaptive feedback by introducing a lightweight, data-driven regression model based on DistilBERT. This architecture proved beneficial because it could learn linguistic and semantic features directly from sample essays, enabling strong generalisation.

Table VIII presents the performance of these regression models on both training and testing datasets.

Table VIII: Benchmarking Metrics for DBR Cycle 4

Split	MAE	R^2	Pearson (r)	Spearman (ρ)	± 0.5 (%)	± 1.0 (%)
Train	0.605	0.495	0.711	0.682	46.9	83.7
Test	0.666	0.354	0.601	0.577	45.2	74.8

E. Metric Analysis for DBR Cycle 4

The changes in Cycle 4 yielded substantial AES improvements compared with Cycles 2 and 3. The MAE essentially halved to 0.666 on unseen essays (test set), a major improvement to Cycle 2 and 3’s best of 1.14, quantifying an average predictive accuracy improvement of 0.474 bands.

Crucially, R^2 became positive for the first time; the model correctly explains 35-49.5% of the data variance in expert-graded essays, compared with performance below the mean in Cycles 2 and 3, characterised by negative R^2 values.

Additionally, we included the analysis of Pearson metrics to help gauge the correctness of bands scaling, achieving 0.601-0.711. Indicating that predictions adhered to the correct numeric spacing, amplifying our MAE values credibility [53].

Similarly, Spearman’s rank correlation was used to assess the model’s ability to understand ordinal essay characteristics, which was vital for validly contributing to AES research [54]. The Spearman values (0.577-0.682) suggest that the band-order relationship was captured reliably, complementing the band-accuracy measures. Both the Spearman and Pearson metrics exceeded 0.60, aligning well with the established benchmarks for AES studies [49].

It should be noted that although the ± 0.5 band accuracy didn’t seem to show much improvement compared to Cycles 2 and 3, the inclusion of the ± 1.0 metric aided in painting a true grading performance indicator. Because Cycle 4 was trained on 1,200 samples and tested on 300 unseen samples, the metrics relayed were more consistent and stable, and in fact showed far greater generalisability than the 100 sampled essays in Cycles 2 and 3.

From a benchmarking metric overview, the DistilBERT regression model improved predictive performance, variance explanation, and correlation with human scoring. Pillaring a strong podium to begin implementing adaptive feedback into the mix.

F. Visual Analysis of DBR Cycle 4 Benchmark Results

To dissect the improvements observed in Table VI, we generated visual analytics of the DistilBERT regression model performance.

Figs 11–14 exhibit scatter plots, box-plot distributions, and confusion matrices across training and testing datasets, furnishing a deeper understanding about the metrics in Table VIII and the impact of transitioning to a transformer architecture.

Figure 11: (Cycle 4). Scatter plot of actual vs predicted scores (train/test samples).

The predictions were notably more tightly grouped around the line of best fit compared to Cycles 2 and 3. During training, the predictions closely followed the best-fit line from bands 4.0 to 7.5, which is supported by strong Pearson (0.711) and Spearman (0.682) correlations.

Most importantly, the model’s scores were more consistent across the IELTS bands, addressing a pivotal issue with rule-based models that showed compressed scores in the middle bands.

Predictably, performance slightly declined in the test split, a common occurrence with unseen data. Nevertheless, the score distribution remained controlled, with an MAE of 0.666. Higher-band essays (7.5–9.0) exhibited mild underprediction, but this was significantly less than in Cycles 2 and 3, where predictions often steeply converged toward bands 6.0–6.5.

Fig. 11 shows a reduced spread, better diagonal alignment, and more precise scoring coverage, confirming that the transformer architecture provided scores that more closely resemble expert grading for IELTS writing.

Figure 12: Box plots of actual vs predicted scores (train/test samples).

Fig. 12’s box plot illustrates the improvement in the model’s score distribution accuracy following the upgrade. During training, the model predicted a median score of 6.82, closely matching the actual median of 6.57,

Figure 14: (Cycle 4). Confusion matrix of actual vs predicted bands (train/test samples).

Fig. 14 illustrates that the regression models demonstrate stable predictive performance across training and testing datasets.

In the training set, residuals remain close to zero, indicating accurate predictions within the 4.0–7.5 band range, with slight deviations in higher-band essays (7.5–9.0).

The test residuals follow this pattern, showing a slightly wider spread as expected for unseen data, but a much more balanced error distribution across the entire IELTS band spectrum.

The model error distribution plots for both train and test data display typically Gaussian shapes with mean values near zero, confirming that the model is not systematically overpredicting or underpredicting.

This controlled spread aligns with the MAE scores detailed in Table VIII and implies that the model generalises well without significant scoring bias.

Overall, the visual analyses confirm the model’s reliability for an effective adaptive feedback system, providing a solid foundation for Cycle’s adaptive feedback implementation.

G. Statistical Analysis of DBR Cycle 5 Results

Table IX: DBR Cycle 5 Pre- and Post-Revision Comparisons

Metric	Value
Essay Pairs	30
Original Mean \pm SD	6.724 ± 0.490
Revised Mean \pm SD	6.784 ± 0.472
Mean Improvement	+0.06015
Essays improved (%)	76.7%
Essays worsened (%)	23.3%
Paired t-test (test statistic, t)	2.714
Paired t-test (probability, p)	0.01106
Wilcoxon signed-rank test	$p = 0.00538$
Cohen's d (paired)	0.504 (medium)
Significant level (α)	0.05

The adaptive feedback implementation in DBR Cycle 5 proved to be a statistically significant positive shift after revision. As indicated by Table IX, adaptive feedback brought about an +0.060 changes across personas. Conducting a paired t-test yielded statistics of $t = 2.714$, and $p = 0.01106$ at significance levels (α) of 0.05, further validating that adaptive feedback was significant for the increase in scoring.

Additionally, due to the smaller size sample (30 essays) being used, the inclusion of the Wilcoxon signed-rank test returning $p = 0.00538$ excludes that there were any violations of normality in the sample set.

The Cohen's d was included to quantify the standard deviation between the two grouped means, being the original mean and the revised mean of the IELTS writing tasks assigned to each persona, reporting a medium effected value of 0.504 suggests that whilst the change is modest, it is still meaningfully relative to the subject variability.

The statistical tests conducted on the comparison of the results pre- and post- adaptive feedback allows us to interpret that the adaptive feedback system was successful in providing consistent gains across the sample. Although the improvements were most marginal 0.25-0.5, even incremental increases in educational setting are particularly relevant, even more so for higher stake exams such as IELTS Preparations where a shift of 0.25-0.5 bands can influence outcomes.

Table X: DBR Cycle 5 Pre- and Post-Revision IELTS Writing Task Band Scores

Persona	Essays	Original Mean	Revised Mean	Δ Mean	% Improved
P1	6	6.4630	6.5460	+0.0830	100%
P2	6	6.6849	6.7313	+0.0463	66.7%
P3	6	6.6544	6.7254	+0.0710	66.7%
P4	6	6.9556	6.9024	-0.0532	50.0%
P5	6	6.8619	7.0155	+0.1536	100%

Examining Table X by persona reveals varied effects across feedback strategies:

- **P1 (Surface edits):** Persona 1 saw 100% essay improvement with mean band improvements of (+0.083). Unmasking that cursory corrections, primarily grammar, spelling, and punctuation, supplied by adaptive feedback consistently resulted in measurable band increases.

- **P2 (Structural) and P3 (Selective):** While both personas saw an increase in mean band score (+0.0463 and +0.0710), changes were less uniform in comparison to alternative revision styles, with only 66.7% essays improving. This implies that although structural and selective modifications were effective, they were not as effective across the domain.
- **P4 (Coherence):** The coherence-focused revision style yielded a small negative average (-0.0532) and only 50% improved. On the exterior this suggests coherence-focused feedback may be riskier although a deeper examination could reveal that targeting remediation towards one IELTS writing rubric is the real risk. Instead, it would have been more beneficial to apply adaptive feedback more holistically.
- **P5 (Conservative):** Persona 5 capitulated 100% improved with the largest mean increase (+0.1536). Conservative safe edits feedback performed to be the most successful at relaying maximal band gains for the sample set.

Regarding pedagogical implications, the persona outcomes illustrate that adaptive feedback strategies must balance both risk and reward. Surface (P1) and conservative (P5) approaches dependably boost scores, whereas narrower targeted interventions (P2, P3, P4) require cautious implementations for consistent and positive outcomes.

This observation supports designing adaptive feedback systems that modulate feedback type based on the student’s baseline performance and multiple revision iterations.

H. Visual Analysis of DBR Cycle 5 Results

To complement the statistical tests discussed in Section G, a visual analysis was performed to verify distributional assumptions, contextualise effect sizes, and explore how adaptive feedback varies across different candidate personas.

While the paired t-test and Wilcoxon signed-rank test confirm that the score improvements are statistically significant, visualisations of these metrics offer deeper insights into score dispersion, symmetry, persona-level variability, and the consistency of progress, enabling statistical inference across the entire sample.

Overall, these figures support the inferential findings by showing that modest yet systematic score gains arise from different revision strategies, rather than from outliers or distributional anomalies.

Figure 15: (Cycle 5). Before vs After Scores: Scatter Plot (Persona Score Grouping)

Fig. 15's scatter plot shows color-coded personas with essay scores before (circles) and after (triangles) adaptive feedback revision across the sample. Most triangle scores are higher than the circle scores, indicating that adaptive feedback positively affected IELTS writing extracts and supporting Table VIII's reported 76.7% essay improvement rate.

Notably, Persona 5 (orange) demonstrated the greatest score increase, highlighting that a conservative revision approach was most beneficial. While the vertical spread appears tight and the standard deviation values of ± 0.490 and ± 0.472 are modest, in the context of a high-stakes exam like IELTS writing, it is appropriate to consider the increase statistically significant.

Figure 16: (Cycle 5). Histogram Distribution of Essay Improvements

Fig. 16 shows the distribution of band-scores after adaptive feedback revisions. The red dashed line indicates zero change, while the green line shows a mean score improvement of 0.060 bands. Most revised essays lie on the positive side, supporting that 76.7% improved.

The right-skewed distribution suggests the feedback mainly enhanced scores, confirmed by a paired t-test with $p=0.01106$, indicating a 1.1% chance results are due to randomness at $\alpha=0.05$.

Since the data aren't perfectly normal, a Wilcoxon signed-rank test was used, with $p=0.00538$, confirming improvements. Cohen's d of 0.504 indicates a medium effect size, about half a standard deviation, with small but consistent gains.

The histogram tail extending to +0.30 suggests more substantial improvements are possible with guided feedback.

Figure 17: (Cycle 5). Box Plot of Score Distributions.

Fig. 17 showcases box plot distributions of essay scoring before and after adaptive feedback, both containing similar IQR spreads spanning 6.5-7.0 and variability values of 0.47-0.49.

The median of revised scores is slightly higher, reflecting a small mean improvement (+0.060). Lower outliers remain around 5.5, and the whiskers and box sizes are nearly identical, indicating that feedback preserves the score variability.

The overlapping distributions suggest the improvement is modest (Cohen's $d = 0.504$). Adaptive feedback raises scores slightly but does not remove low-performing essays.

Fig. 17 illustrates that adaptive feedback implementation produces small, consistent gains rather than large jumps in performance.

Figure 18: (Cycle 5). Scatter plot of Measured Improvement: (Persona Grouping)

Fig. 18 illustrates the extent of improvement, categorised by persona, clearly visualising the differences in revision styles across personas. Persona 5 consistently demonstrates positive score gains, whereas Persona 4 tends to cluster around zero or negative change, especially for higher-scoring essays.

Overall, Fig. 18 indicates that the level of improvement is influenced more by the feedback approach than the initial score. This supports the conclusion that adaptive feedback results in modest but meaningful improvements, with some strategies proving more effective than others.

I. Summary of DBR Cycles

The research used a DBR methodology to develop and evaluate an automated IELTS writing assessment system. Empirical findings from iterative cycles identified technical and pedagogical limitations, guiding targeted redesigns to improve grading reliability, generalisation, and instructional usefulness for IELTS candidates.

Early cycles, especially DBR cycles 2 and 3, established the system architecture and evaluated rule-based and hybrid grading methods. Analyses revealed limited accuracy, score compression, and poor alignment with expert scoring, especially for higher-band essays. Although incremental improvements were made through refined linguistic features, these approaches reached a performance ceiling, prompting a shift away from rule-driven assessment.

DBR Cycle 4 introduced a DistillBERT transformer regression model, significantly improving evaluation metrics, including reduced MAE, positive R^2 , and stronger correlations, making it more suitable for precise IELTS essay grading. Visual analysis confirmed better score distribution and stability across unseen data, establishing a reliable scoring backbone for pedagogical interventions.

Building on this, DBR Cycle 5 tested whether adaptive feedback could support essay improvements in IELTS writing. Using a controlled framework and a locked test set, statistical testing unveiled a small but significant improvement in predicted band scores, supported by visual evidence of consistent gains.

Although modest, these results demonstrate that adaptive feedback can produce meaningful educational effects in high-stakes assessments when correctly aligned with learner revision behaviour.

VII. Discussion

This study investigated how automated scoring combined with adaptive feedback impacts the IELTS Writing Task 2 utilising DBR cycles to continuously improve the research quality. Early cycles leverage rule-based grading systems that were deemed unreliable, producing inconsistent scores compression around middle bands (5-5.6.5), and metrics such 1.14 MAE for scoring and negative R^2 values in Cycles 2 and 3.

Later cycles incorporated a DistilBERT transformer model with addition of a regression model (Cycle 4), improving overall predictive performance, delivering a solid predictive base of 0.666 MAE as well as positively reasoning about essays scoring R^2 values of 0.495 on the training set, and 0.354 on the test set demonstrating the model could generally reason well about data variability.

The solid predictive base permitted the incorporation of adaptive feedback (Cycle 5), which was tested operating persona revision style experiments, generating modest but statistically significant score improvements (mean = +0.060 bands, paired $t(29) = 2.714$, $p = 0.01106$ and Wilcoxon $p = 0.00538$).

Aligned with Ludwig et al. [44], this research study agrees that BERT transformer models are better suited for AES, encapsulating and generalising sensitive linguistic essays more precisely than pure regressive models, supporting Ludwig et al.'s claim that the transformer AES implementation correlates greater with human assessors.

Further supporting Ludwig, Cycle 4's transformer model resembled well with expert-scorers, benchmarking values like Pearson (r) values of 0.60-0.71 and Spearman (ρ) of 0.58-0.68 depicting both quality linear score spacing and ordinal band ranking.

Moreover, this research also supports studies conducted by Ifenthaler [43] reporting stronger performance and more precise score distribution variability when switching to transformer models with a regression head in DBR cycle 4 replacing the rule and feature approach in DBR cycles 2 and 3.

Contrasting platforms more fixated around lower-stakes interactions such as Duolingo [10] or English advocacy practice such ELSA Speak [9]. This research emphasises a void on contextualised, IELTS-specific learning platforms which supply guidance and preparation for IELTS writing tasks.

The learner persona experimentation underpins that revision behaviour is a negotiating factor for yielding maximal performance gains through targeted feedback. Conservative (P1) and cursory (P5) revision strategies relaying the most consistent and essay score improvements, with holistic mean improvements of +0.083 and +0.1536.

On the contrary, revision strategies solely focusing on coherence (P4) occasionally led to score deterioration (-0.0532) and improvements occurred for only 50% of essays, implying that revision tactics neglecting holistic essay structure may be pedagogically counterproductive.

Results similarly mirrored Bai's [17] controlled classroom study which yielded high post-test improvement in lexical resource and grammar accuracy following writing guidance led by ChatGPT, but only slight inconsistent improvements occurred when following coherence guidance. This research backs Bai's claim that higher-order cognitive writing demands are required for a deeper structuring rather than surface level refinements such as lexical resource and grammatical corrections.

Pedagogically adaptive feedback systems in critical writing scenarios should focus on safety, explainability, and incremental remediation, as shown by conservative grammatical and lexical corrections, while aggressive restructuring can sometimes negate potential improvements [17]. Additionally, results favoured a hybrid model where automated feedback is supplementary to instructor guidance rather than replacing it entirely.

Although this study was measuring the influence of adaptive feedback was controlled through persona-based case studies, system design remains crucial for smoothly integrating adaptive feedback into a learning platform, especially for ESL learners when tailoring for exams like the IELTS. Aligning with cognitive load theory and prior UI research that emphasise structured feedback hierarchies, avoiding divided attention and task ambiguity [21].

Research limitations include the reliance on a small test set of 30 writing samples and simulated persona revisions, opposed to real IELTS candidates, limiting potential insights into long-term pedagogical effects. Although the DistilBERT model achieved good precision, underpredictions lingered between higher band ranges, particularly the 8.0-9.0 bands.

Despite better accuracy than Cycles 2 and 3 rule-based methodologies, persistent underpredictions could affect the platform's usefulness for more advanced writers. However, since the large majority of IELTS candidates are more focused on passing rather than achieving perfect scores, deeming underprediction to be a less critical limitation.

Finally, system's diagnostic reports statistically and visually, support pedagogical unbiased effectiveness and writing improvements, validation from official IELTS examiners would be essential for future system refinements.

Future research should mainly focus on feedback from extensive real IELTS candidate studies, tracking essay improvements across multiple longer-term revision cycles, assessing score changes and perceived platform usefulness.

Subsequently, experiments that break down individual IELTS feedback writing components such as grammar, lexical resource, coherence, and task achievement on a sufficiently large scale could reveal which factors most significantly enhanced IELTS scores. They can also identify which rubric elements candidates emphasise most, highlighting the key areas needing immediate intervention.

When conducting these user studies, it is crucial to consider potential biases related to writing standards, especially due to heavy reliance on AI technologies. Counteractively implementing anti-detection measures, like AI detection, is essential to eliminate non-authentic examples and preserve the validity of the case study [18].

VIII. Conclusion

Above, we analysed and discussed the benefits of curating a IELTS writing task learning platform featuring AES in conjunction with pedagogically aligned adaptive feedback through utilising DBR cycles to progress automated essay scoring from rule-based systems to a transformer-based model with a regression head.

Early cycles identified the limitations of feature and rule-based methods, while integrating a DistilBERT transformer model crafted a more stable predictive foundation. Adding adaptive feedback to this setup showed that even modest, statistically significant essay improvements are possible when feedback is based on consistent automated assessment.

Notably, persona-based adaptive feedback revealed that learner revision behaviour influences feedback success. Conservative grammatical and lexical guidance delivered the most consistent gains, while narrowly focused coherence interventions were less reliable, highlighting the risks of aggressive essay restructuring [17].

The findings suggest that adaptive feedback should complement human instruction rather than replace it, especially for rubric elements like Task Achievement and Coherence and Cohesion that need restructuring or deeper analysis, which would benefit from guidance and interpretation that align with pedagogical goals. Conversely, elements such as Grammatical Range and Accuracy, and Lexical Resource can be addressed effectively with minimal human intervention.

Future research could explore embedding real ESL candidate evaluations and human-in-the-loop validation to assess long-term learning transfer and fairness in assessment contexts.

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